

A Note on Powell and Whittaker's Method for the Determination of Pentosans.

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The pentosan content of substances is generally determined by distilling with dilute hydrochloric acid, either directly or in a current of steam and estimating the furfural that distills over. Several methods have been proposed for the determination of the furfural in solution. Amongst the most important are:—

(1) *The official method.* (“*Methods of Analysis of Association of Official Agricultural Chemists*” 1930, 3rd Edn., p. 284). The furfural is condensed with phloroglucinol in acid solution and the furfural-phloroglucide filtered, washed, dried and weighed. From this weight, the amount of furfural is calculated by using Kröber's tables.

(2) *The bromine absorption method*, in which the furfural is allowed to react with bromine, when each molecule of furfural absorbs four atoms. From the amount of bromine absorbed the quantity of furfural is calculated according to the above reaction.

Pervier and Gertner (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1923, 15, 1167, 1255) in an elaborate review of the previous literature, have condemned the various methods for various reasons and have recommended the bromine absorption method to be the best. Even in this case, they failed to get satisfactory results when excess of bromine was employed. Hence they use only the exact amount of bromine required, the end point being determined electrometrically. Their procedure is somewhat tedious. The author has also found the official phloroglucinol method highly unsatisfactory for small quantities, whereas the bromine absorption method gave very satisfactory results. Powell and Whittaker (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1924, 43, 35 T) have employed excess of bromine and obtained good results. Deshpande (*J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1930, 13A, 110) after a comparative study of several methods, concludes that the bromine absorption method gives the best results. More recently, after the author had finished all his work, Kline and Acree (*E. S. R.*, 1932, 67, 364) also conclude that the excess bromine titration method is speedy and accurate over wide ranges of concentration. When Powell and Whittaker's

method was employed by the author erratic results were obtained. Lack of proportionality in bromine absorption with varying concentrations of bromine in the reaction mixture was noticed. This defect was eventually traced to the influence of temperature and when the temperature was regulated highly satisfactory and very concordant results were obtained.

The improved bromine absorption method (*vide infra*), besides giving very accurate and concordant results, even when only very small quantities of furfural are present, is also far simpler to manipulate, especially when a large number of determinations have to be made than the official phloroglucinal method.

FIG. 1.

EXPERIMENTAL.

As the result of preliminary titrations the time of bromination was fixed at 90 minutes (Fig. 1).

Preliminary titrations, carried out according to Powell and Whittaker, showed that bromine absorption became relatively less as the concentration of furfural in solution increased (Table I).

TABLE I.

Influence of concentration of furfural and bromine in the reaction mixture.

<i>N</i> /10-Br ₂ used.		Furfural solution used			
		5 c.c.	10 c.c.	15 c.c.	20 c.c.
20 c.c.	<i>N</i> /10-Br ₂ absorbed				
30	by total furfural	3.85 c.c.	7.55 c.c.	10.60 c.c.	13.45 c.c.
20	Do	3.90	7.70	11.25	14.55
30	per c.c. of furfural	0.77	0.75	0.71	0.67
	Do	0.78	0.77	0.75	0.73

The above table shows that with the same initial concentration of bromine there is a progressive decline in the absorption with an increase in the furfural concentration. It also proves that with an increase in the initial bromine concentration there is an increase in the absorption, the concentration of furfural remaining the same.

Preliminary titrations also showed that the bromine absorption was influenced considerably by a temperature factor. A standard solution of furfural was prepared and the bromine absorption of equal quantities was measured at two different temperatures. The figures are given in Table II.

TABLE II.

Influence of temperature on bromine absorption of furfuraldehyde.

Quantity of furfural used.	<i>N</i> /10-Br ₂ .	Br ₂ absorbed at 15° by		Br ₂ absorbed at 30° by	
		Total soln.	per c.c.	Total soln.	per c.c.
5 c.c.	25 c.c.	3.50 c.c.	0.70 cc.	3.70 c.c.	0.74 c.c.
10	"	6.70	0.67	7.50	0.75
15	"	9.25	0.62	11.30	0.75
20	"	11.55	0.58	14.90	0.75
15	50	10.70	0.71	11.20	0.75
20	"	13.50	0.68	15.00	0.75

From the above table the following points are noted:—

- (1) At the higher temperature absorption is greater.
- (2) At the higher temperature absorption is quite proportional to the amount of furfural, the initial bromine concentration being the same in all cases.

(3) At the lower temperature absorption is not proportional to the amount of furfural, the relative absorption decreasing with the increase in concentration of the same.

(4) The absorption at 15° using 50 c. c. of bromine is distinctly higher than that obtained with 25 c.c. But even 50 c. c. of bromine at this temperature do not raise the absorption up to the 30° level. On the other hand, working at 30° this very large excess of bromine (50 c.c.) do not raise the absorption above that obtained with only 25 c.c.

To ascertain the optimum temperature of bromination an accurate standard solution of very pure furfural was prepared and the bromine absorption of equal quantities with identical bromine concentrations was measured at different temperatures. The results are given in Table III.

TABLE III.

Bromine absorption of furfural at different temperatures.
(1 C.c. furfural solution contains 0.0004565 g. furfural).

Standard furfural solution used.	N/10-Br ₂ .	N/10-bromine absorbed at.			
		15°	20°	25°	30°
5 c.c.	10 c.c.	0.90 c.c.	0.95 c.c.	0.95 c.c.	0.95 c.c.
10	10	1.80	1.99	1.85	1.90
25	10	3.95	4.35	4.60	4.75
50	20	8.05	8.80	9.40	9.55
50	50	9.00	9.45	—	9.55

From the above table it can be seen that 30° is the optimum temperature for bromination. At this temperature the bromine absorption is proportional to the concentration of furfural and is unaffected by variations in bromine concentration.

Further at 30° 10 c.c. of the furfural solution absorb 4.75 c.c. N/10-bromine. This corresponds to an absorption of 4 atoms of bromine by each molecule of furfural. Therefore by measuring the bromine absorption by a solution of furfural at 30° and by taking 1 c.c. of N/10-bromine to be equal to 0.0024 g. of furfural the accurate estimation of any furfural solution may be carried out.

The above experiments further show that at 30° a definite degree of bromination has been attained and this is not exceeded by increasing the bromine concentration even considerably.

At lower temperatures, especially with higher quantities of furfural, this degree of bromination was not attained by using quantities of bromine equal to those employed at 30°. In this case, however, an increase of bromine concentration was followed by increased absorption. It is remarkable that at 15° even a considerable increase of bromine concentration has failed to produce the degree of bromination attained at 30° with much lower bromine concentrations. The temperature factor is, therefore, most potent in this reaction.

Comparison of the phloroglucinol precipitation method and the modified bromine absorption method for small quantities of furfural.—A series of experiments were done to compare the relative accuracies of the above methods for small quantities of furfural.

A solution of pure furfural was prepared and used for all the following tests. Equal quantities were taken and estimated by the official precipitation method, a modified precipitation method and by the modified bromine absorption method. In the modified precipitation method, the precipitation is carried out in 200 c.c. instead of the 400 c.c., all the other conditions remaining the same. A correction of 0.0026 (being half the official correction for the 400 c.c. volume) was made. The results are given in Table IV.

TABLE IV.

Recovery of pure furfural by different methods.

Pure furfural taken.	Furfural found by		
	Phloroglucinol precipitation in		Bromine absorption at 30°.
	400 c.c. vol.	200 c.c. vol.	
0.00228 g.	0.00424	0.00302	0.00228
0.00456	0.00566	0.00496	0.00456
0.01140	0.01277	0.01142	0.01140
0.02280	0.02395	0.02390	0.02292

It is readily seen from the above figures that (i) the official method fails with small quantities, (ii) the modification improves it somewhat, (iii) the bromine absorption method gives very satisfactory results. At higher concentrations of furfural the official and the

bromine absorption method agree. A further proof of the failure of the official method for small quantities is given below.

In the determination of pentosans in a sample of fodder, the distillate was collected in four equal fractions of 300 c.c. each at intervals of an hour. They were separately tested for furfural content by the official phloroglucinol method and the bromine absorption method. The results are given in Table V.

TABLE V.

Comparison of the official and bromine absorption methods.

Distillation fraction.	Furfural as determined by	
	Bromine absorption.	Phloroglucinol pption.
1	0.1375	0.1395
2	0.0144	0.0220
3	0.0079	0.0150
4	0.0054	0.0103
Total	<u>0.1652</u>	<u>0.1868</u>

This shows that the official precipitation method gives much higher values. With small quantities, the results are nearly 100% more than the bromine absorption method. Though there is likelihood of the bromine absorption figures being themselves slightly higher, owing to the distillation of other bromine absorbing substances along with the furfural the official method gives far higher values and is, therefore, useless. This is due to the addition of the correction, which in these small quantities absolutely vitiates the result.

In another experiment, the distillate was collected in two fractions of 600 c.c. each and the furfural content was determined in each of the fractions separately and also after mixing in the entire distillate by both the methods. In this case, the phloroglucinol precipitation was done in 200 c.c. volume to minimise the errors (*cf.* Table VI).

TABLE VI.

Expt. No. 1.			Expt. No. 2.		
Furfural as determined by			Furfural as determined by		
Distillation fraction.	Bromine absorption.	Phloroglucinol precipitation.	Distillation fraction.	Bromine absorption.	Phloroglucinol precipitation.
1	0·1213	0·1220	1	0·1300	0·1313
2	0·0277	0·0364	2	0·0169	0·0239
Total	<u>0·1490</u>	<u>0·1584</u>	Total	<u>0·1469</u>	<u>0·1552</u>
	0·1490	0·1360		0·1469	0·1328

Here also it can be seen that whereas the bromine absorption method gives concordant results, the precipitation method gives higher values in the separate fractions, but curiously enough gives lower values in the mixed entire distillate. In the first fraction, both the values agree while in the second the precipitation method gives nearly 50 % more in spite of the lower correction figure.

All the above data go to show the complete constancy and accuracy of the furfural estimations when carried out by the bromine absorption method at 30°.

SUMMARY

1. It is shown that at 30° the absorption of bromine by furfural is proportional to the quantity of the same irrespective of the bromine concentration in the reaction mixture, corresponding to the absorption of 4 atoms of bromine per molecule of furfural.

2. It is also shown that for small quantities of furfural the official method of precipitation with phloroglucinol fails to give accurate values, whereas the proposed bromine absorption method gives reliable figures.

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